

A STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES IN HOSPITAL, GANDHIPURAM

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Abstract: Job satisfaction refers to one's feeling towards one's job. If the employees expectations are fulfilled (or) the employees get higher than what he/she feels satisfied. If the job satisfaction increases organization commitment will increased. This results in the higher productivity.

Keywords: job satisfaction, productivity, organizational commitment.

1. INTRODUCTION

About the topic:

Job satisfaction is a person's overall evaluation of his or her job as favorable or unfavorable. It reflects an attitude toward one's job and hence includes affect, cognitions, and behavioral tendencies. Job satisfaction is a widely studied and central variable in many theories about organizational phenomena, and it is related to many factors that are important for human resource management such as performance, counterproductive work behavior, turnover, and employee health.

Five facts of job satisfaction:

According to Werner job satisfaction has five facets, which can be put together to measure a Job Descriptive Index (JDI) as follows:

- The work itself – responsibility, interest and growth.
- Quality of supervision – technical help and social support.
- Relationships with co-workers – social harmony and respect.
- Promotion opportunities – chances for further advancement.
- Pay – adequacy of pay and perceived equity vis-à-vis others.

Importance of job satisfaction:

According to Schermerhorn the importance of job satisfaction can be viewed in the context of two decisions people make about their work. The first is the decision to belong – that is, join and remain a member of an organization. The second is the decision to perform – that is, to work hard in pursuit of high levels of task performance. Job satisfaction influences absenteeism or the failure of people to attend work. Job satisfaction can also affect turnover or decisions by people to terminate their employment

This primary objective can further be divided into the following sub-objectives:

1. To help the organization to attain its goals effectively and efficiently by providing competent and motivated employees.

2. To utilize the available human resources effectively.
3. To increase to the fullest the employee's job satisfaction and self-actualization.

Human resource challenges:

1. Compliance with Laws and Regulation

Keeping up with changing employment laws is a struggle for business owners. Many choose to ignore employment laws, believing they don't apply to their business. But doing so could mean audits, lawsuits, and possibly even the demise of your company.

2. Management Changes

As a business grows, its strategies, structure, and internal processes grow with it. Some employees have a hard time coping with these changes. A lot of companies experience decreased productivity and morale during periods of change.

3. Workforce Training and Development

Investing in the training and development of lower-level employees is another common HR problem. Some businesses have trouble finding the resources to do so. Employees on the front lines are some of your hardest workers, and may not have the time to take a training course.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. According to **Prabhakar⁴ (2016)**, the Job satisfaction leads to better employee loyalty and holds the major role in this equation but it is not the only factor that affects loyalty. He also discover that workplace environment which consist of interpersonal relationships, transparency, stability of tenure, employee empowerment and growth opportunities affect the relationship between job satisfaction and employee loyalty positively.
2. According to **Frempong et al⁴ (2018)**, the impact of job satisfaction on employee's loyalty. The study concluded that job satisfaction showed a significant impact on loyalty and commitment in the manufacturing and mining sector. Workplace environment showed a positive relationship and a significant impact on job satisfaction resonates the working atmosphere gives pleasure to employees to do their best to maximize performance.
3. According to **Khuong and Tien⁵ (2013)**, the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational loyalty of employees in banking industry. Quantitative approach was the major method used. It was derived that higher levels of satisfaction, supervisor support, fringe benefits, teamwork, working environment, and training were positively associated with the higher level of organizational loyalty.
4. According to **Pandey and Khare⁶ (2012)**, the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Further the study also finds the comparison of employee loyalty in manufacturing and service industry.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is a systematic, formal, rigorous and precise process employed to gain solutions to problems or to discover and interpret new facts and relationships. This chapter explains the methods adopted by the researcher, for a study on "Attrition analysis on nurses and admin staffs". It deals with the research approach, research design, population, sample size, sampling technique, procedure for the data collection and statistical analysis.

Table showing the respondent's gender

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO.OF.RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Male	8	8
2	Female	92	92
3	others	0	0
TOTAL		100	100

INTERPRETATION

The above table shows that 8% of the respondents are male and 92% of the respondents are female.

Table showing the respondent’s age

S.NO	PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Less than 25	60	60
2	26-45	39	39
3	45 above	1	1
TOTAL		100	100

INTERPRETATION

The above table shows that 60% of the respondents age are less than 25, 39% of the respondents age are 26-45,1% of the respondents age are 45 above.

4. SUGGESTIONS

1. The management must give promotion based on merit, educational qualification and experience and if these factors are given more care, the organization can maintain good workers with high level of satisfaction.
2. The study reveals that the educational qualification of employees was related to job satisfaction. So the management should take steps to further studies of employees. The management may give additional leave to the employees for attend the course work with pay.
3. Management must conduct series of training programs based on the skills and knowledge required, content and the types of category of employees.
4. Organization should conduct a job satisfaction survey at least once in a year and based on the findings corrective steps to be taken to improve the employees.

5. CONCLUSION

Employee job satisfaction is critical to the success of any organization. In most cases, as studies have shown, demographic characteristics of age, gender, educational level, years of experience on the current job, and ethnicity do impact an employee’s job satisfaction. However, in this study, that is not the case and this finding is consistent with other studies. Job satisfaction means different things to different people and in fact, it is a collection of different facets or aspects of a job that the employee values bring him/her satisfaction.

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